

KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND ROLE OF KRC: A CASE STUDY

Kailas Narsing Chavan: PhD Research Scholars, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda

Abstract:

Knowledge comes in many shapes and sizes. It can be stored in databases, printed on paper, integrated into an organization's policies, procedures and reports, or contained within an employee's memory. Generally, knowledge management is a discipline that promotes an integrated approach to identifying, managing and sharing all of an organization's information assets, regardless of how or where they are located. It is strategic in nature and involves the careful interaction of people, process and technology. The paper then addresses the very difficult issue of measuring the return on investment of a KM strategy and outlines the short and long term strategies for assessing knowledge management. Finally, the critical role that information professionals can play in knowledge management is outlined, and the paper concludes by encouraging special librarians to play a much more active role in this area or else run the risk of being marginalized.

Key words: Knowledge Management, Categories of knowledge, Knowledge Management in Knowledge Centre, Developing Information Skills Role of KRC

Introduction:

Knowledge economy is a knowledge-based economy. In the knowledge economy era, the management refers to effectively identify, acquire, develop, resolve, use, store and share knowledge, to create an approach to transforming and sharing of tacit and explicit knowledge, and to raise the emergency and innovation capability by utilizing the wisdom of the team. Since knowledge has become the driving force for social development, the attention of the society to information and knowledge is rising and people's demands for information and knowledge are increasing step by step. This has provided a good environment for Knowledge Centre development . Moreover, as information and knowledge has become an important productive factor for the modern economic system, the society will inevitably require intensified management of information and knowledge..

How to manage knowledge will become an important subject facing Knowledge Centre in the near future. Knowledge management in Knowledge Centre should be focused on effective research and development of knowledge, creation of knowledge bases, exchange and sharing of knowledge between Knowledge Centre staffs (including its users), training of Knowledge Centre staff, speeding up explicit processing of the implicit knowledge and realizing of its sharing.

What is knowledge management: Knowledge management is a viewed by many as something new, and this is far from the truth. There are as many different definitions of knowledge management as there are people on this earth. As with any evolving issue, theorists tend to get caught up designing definitions and labels which invariably take people away from the practical issues at hand.

The concept of knowledge is certainly not new. For centuries, master craftsmen have painstakingly taught their trade to apprentices, owners of family businesses have passed their wisdom onto their children and workers have exchanged ideas and know-how on the job. Knowledge management requires description, not definition. A colleague of mine from Ernst and Young in the United States and, a leading KM thinker/practitioner, Rudy Ruggles, has identified the following items as integral components of KM:

1. Generating new knowledge
2. Accessing valuable knowledge from outside sources
3. Using accessible knowledge in decision making
4. Embedding knowledge in processes, products, and/or services
5. Representing knowledge in documents, databases, and software

6. Facilitating knowledge growth through culture and incentives
7. Transferring existing knowledge into other parts of the organisation
8. Measuring the value of knowledge assets and/or impact of knowledge management

Categories of knowledge: Knowledge can take many different forms and have different meanings to each individual organization. We generally find that there are consistently three categories of knowledge:

1. Internal Knowledge;
2. Customer Knowledge; and
3. Market Knowledge.

Internal Knowledge: "If only we knew what we know": there is a vast wealth of information and knowledge which resides within each organization, but most organizations do not know where it is when they need it. As a result, many employees waste time trying to find out if something exists, then give up in frustration and reinvent the wheel.

Customer Knowledge: "If only we knew as much as our customers": customers invariably know more about the organizations they do business with than the business knows about its customers. Whilst all businesses recognize that they are nothing without their customers, they rarely fully capitalize on the customer knowledge that their employees informally collect daily.

Market Knowledge: "If only we knew what was going on out there": many organizations tend to operate in blissful ignorance of the broader market in which they compete. As a result, they can be less responsive and flexible, and more exposed to market and economic threat.

Value for knowledge management: Organizations are embracing knowledge management for a variety of reasons. Generally speaking, organizations will need to effectively manage their knowledge if they display any of the following characteristics:

1. Rapid growth
2. Multiple concurrent projects
3. Loss of corporate memory
4. Geographic dispersion
5. Strategic mind set
6. Culture of accountability/ responsibility/ excellence
7. Global market place
8. Competition

The core of organizations moving forward with knowledge initiatives is the value proposition. This provides the focus - the explicit business rationale for the knowledge strategy generally or each specific knowledge project. Organizations will invariably have quite different reasons for wanting to achieve best practice and leverage information and knowledge for competitive gain. Operational Excellence

Benefits and drivers of knowledge management: Typically, organizations are returning the following benefits from the knowledge management initiatives:

1. Leverage existing resources for competitive edge
2. Enhanced innovation
3. Better decision making
4. Reducing product to market cycle time
5. Increasing flexibility/responsiveness
6. Increasing ability to be proactive
7. Long term return on investment
8. Reducing operating costs
9. Increasing profits
10. Defending market share against existing competitors
11. Growing revenue

12. Better positioning for regulatory/ legislative changes
13. Making globalisation decisions
14. Better staff retention
15. Sharing best practice
16. Cost reduction
17. Defending market share against new entrants
18. Developing new products and services
19. Assessing corporate value before mergers and acquisitions

Barriers to effective knowledge management:

Whilst many organizations are effectively embracing knowledge management strategies, the road is not always smooth. Clients around the world identify the following key barriers to successfully implementing knowledge initiatives:

- Management sponsorship - without top down support, organizational wide knowledge management has little to no chance of success. Despite the best effort of staff trying to change from below, knowledge must be viewed as integral to the ongoing development of the business if it is to be truly successful.
- Culture - most organizations do not have a culture that naturally supports the sharing of knowledge, even knowledge intensive organizations. The cultural aspects of the organization must be addressed at a senior level as part of the holistic approach to managing knowledge.
- People management - a major barrier to effective knowledge management in many organizations is the failure to address the people aspect. Clear communication, change management, performance management, and appropriate incentive schemes must be considered as part of the strategy.
- Technology - whilst technology is the ultimate enabler to effective knowledge management, it can equally be a major barrier. Organizations who make do with existing technology or go and buy "knowledge" solutions before identifying the broader strategy run the risk of failure.

Characteristics of Knowledge Management in Knowledge Centre:

The role of knowledge management in Knowledge Centre will become more and more important along with the development of knowledge economy. It is a new management mode, boasts the following superiority and characteristics incomparable with conventional management:

Human Resource Management Is the Core of Knowledge Management in . The most important resource in the knowledge economy system is the talents who grasp knowledge. The talent competition has become the focus of market competition in the knowledge economy era. In the knowledge economy era, the Knowledge Centre will attach importance to vocational training and lifelong education of Knowledge Centre staffs to raise their scientific knowledge level and ability of acquiring and innovating knowledge. They also will and fully respect the human value, guide and bring into play wisdom potentialities of Knowledge Centre staffs, take developing knowledge resources in the brains of Knowledge Centre staffs as an important way for rising work efficiency. An all-round improvement of Knowledge Centre staff's quality and positioning of the human value will become important objectives of knowledge management in Knowledge Centre.

Knowledge Centre is to Promote Knowledge Innovation:

Knowledge innovation is the core of the knowledge economy society. As bases for collection, processing, storage and distribution of knowledge and information, Knowledge Centre represent an indispensable link in the scientific system chain, an important link in the knowledge innovation. Secondly, Knowledge Centre take part in scientific research process directly. The Knowledge Centre work is a component of knowledge innovation. Thirdly, Knowledge Centre must pay attention to diffusion and conversion of knowledge. They act as bridges for turning the results of knowledge innovation into realistic productive forces. Knowledge management in Knowledge Centre is to promote relationship in and between Knowledge Centre, between Knowledge Centre and user, to strengthen knowledge internetworking and to quicken knowledge flow. In the knowledge economy

era, Knowledge Centre will carry out researches on development and application of information resources, construction of virtual Knowledge Centre, protection of intellectual property rights in the electronic era etc., thus founding the base for knowledge innovation .

Tool for Knowledge Management in Knowledge Centre :

Knowledge acquisition is the starting point of knowledge management in Knowledge Centre. The application of information technologies enlarges the scope of knowledge acquisition, rises knowledge acquisition speed and reduces knowledge acquisition cost. It is impossible to accomplish such important tasks by using man's brains only in the modern society in which the knowledge changes with each passing day. It will be possible to link closely knowledge sources and knowledge workers by computer networks, thus constructing knowledge networks in Knowledge Centre based on realization of single-point informatisation .

Contents of Knowledge Management in Knowledge Centre:

As a completely new method of management, knowledge management in Knowledge Centre leaves much to be desired in its theoretical system. In my opinion, knowledge management in Knowledge Centre should include such respects as follows:

Knowledge Innovation Management:

Knowledge innovation management in Knowledge Centre refers to the management of the production, diffusion and transfer of knowledge as well as of the network systems constructed by related institutions and organizations. It includes three aspects, namely, theoretical innovation management of knowledge, technical innovation management and organizational innovation management.

Theoretical innovation management is to enrich and enlarge the theoretical and practical research fields of Knowledge Centre science and information science through pursuing the latest development trends in Knowledge Centre science the world over. Technical innovation management is to manage the network systems constructed by institutions and organizations that relate to the full course of technical innovation. In their evolution from conventional Knowledge Centre to electronic Knowledge Centre, or digital Knowledge Centre, Knowledge Centre should make technical breakthroughs and progress and build up technical facilities to support knowledge management. Organizational innovation management is to create a set of effective organizational management systems adaptable to the requirements in the electronic Knowledge Centre era to support and strengthen knowledge management activities, by optimizing the functional departments and operation procedures of Knowledge Centre.

In these systems, it firstly requires that leaders who take charge of knowledge management activities should undertake to formulate the management plans and coordinate all knowledge management related activities. Secondly, it requires establishment of special leading groups of knowledge flow for accomplishing all tasks relating to knowledge management activities. Electronic resources committees are established composed of various types of specialists to take charge of evaluating, procuring and creating the electronic resources on the one hand, and coordinating activities of business departments and spurring them on to close cooperation in such fields as procurement and organization of the electronic information resources as well as providing services on the other hand. New roles and skills for information management

Some corporate Knowledge Centre are being reinvented as s, often with bigger budgets (for example, in the 'big six' consultancies). Nevertheless, their future is by no means assured as there is no shortage of other people ready to take on these tasks. Information professionals are seen in a support role, as service-oriented but not value-oriented - they don't understand the impact they can have on the business, nor do they act on this. The core skills of Knowledge Centre and information professionals are both relevant and essential in organizations today, but they are often under-utilized and under-valued. (Corrall 2000 pg 8).

Joseph Horvath (2000 pg 47) notes that "because of the limit on the time and attention that knowledgeable people can devote to knowledge management activities, firms within a number of

industries (eg professional services, information technology, pharmaceuticals) have begun to experiment with a new type of support role - the 'knowledge integrator' or 'knowledge co-Ordinator'. Although the particulars vary, knowledge co-ordinators are generally responsible for collecting, reshaping, and disseminating the information and knowledge that others in the firm produce in the course of their work. Knowledge co-ordinators also function as intermediaries, putting knowledgeable people in touch with those who need to draw upon their knowledge".

Information professionals already have the 'core' information management skills required to manage knowledge once it becomes 'explicit': 'the process for explicit assets is to identify, catalogue and optimize the availability of the artefacts in which the knowledge is stored.' (Snowden, 1998 pg 13).

The greater challenge for information professionals is managing the 'tacit' intuitions and 'know-how' knowledge workers acquire through years of experience and practice. Tacit knowledge transfer involves people, and social skills such as communication, and it is not always possible, or appropriate, to 'capture' tacit knowledge and treat it as an explicit 'knowledge artefact' (Sbarcea, 2000).

Managing knowledge requires a mix of technical, organizational and interpersonal skills. The mix and emphasis varies according to responsibilities, but everyone involved needs to be able to understand the business, communicate effectively and have at least basic competence in handling information and using IT. (Corrall 2000) Although information service professionals are not always prominently involved at the outset of KM initiatives, many organizations have brought them in at a later stage, when the ongoing management of Intranet 'information architecture' and 'knowledge content' usually emerges as the major challenge. "The need to structure and codify information, to have a common language, and to manage selective dissemination of information, has highlighted information specialists' skills in indexing systems, thesaurus construction, and user profiling for customized alerting", said Jeff Sussman, CEO of Delphi Consulting in Australia at the One Umbrella executive breakfast in April 2000.

Creating an infrastructure:

- Establishing a knowledge management team
- Looking at tools that will help users locate pieces of knowledge regardless of format
- Developing and maintaining a policy manual and associated procedures
- Recruitment of KM consultant
- Purchase of KM software
- Writing policy documents that include knowledge management

Establishing integrated systems and networks to share knowledge:

- Organization linked to national and global knowledge network
- Research tracking system
- Intranet development
- Development of full-text searching for organization's internal file
- Precedents and opinions database established
- Intranet to link company sources of information together
- Attempts to streamline related IT projects in the company and provide an interface
- Creation of a staff 'yellow pages' showing expertise and skills
- Setting up QM system which documents particular ways of doing certain options based on past experiences
- E-mail sharing

Fostering organisational participation and sharing of ideas:

- Reporting on conferences attended
- Brainstorming meetings to solve issues
- Selective and directional use of internet resources
- Involvement of managing partners in precedent development

- Social activities
- Collaborative approach to ideas generation and problem solving
- Sharing of best practices in company forums

Developing Information Skills:

- Teaching information literacy skills, search strategies and record keeping skills
- Empowering individuals to search for information
- Providing training courses to staff
- Developing understanding of the various sectors of the company
- Making staff aware of resources available

Information analysis:

- Analysis of relevant census data
- Analysis of statistics
- After action reviews
- Using data collected in client records to monitor trends
- Analysis of how clients approach software systems

Information capture and consolidation:

- Establishing a system for staff to notaries documents
- Thought mapping
- Mapping work flows
- Guidance notes attached to documents which capture senior expertise
- Leverage of best practices across geographies
- Business process documentation
- Gathering information about how people do things

Organization-wide or Strategic Initiatives:

- Preparation of a corporate plan which articulates KM processes
- Involvement of information staff in development of strategic plan
- Involvement of key Knowledge Centre staff in development of strategic plans with other senior Council Staff. Such including an understanding of operations of various sectors of Council working documents. The meanings behind them not just receiving of them. This with a view to a better overall management plan production and content for organizations.

Conclusion:

This study described the notion of knowledge and knowledge management and investigated the roles of knowledge Centre as knowledge professionals for obtaining organizational goals. The knowledge professional position will continue to evolve as the knowledge infrastructure develops. The precise role of the knowledge professional will depend on the organization structure and knowledge needs. The emphasis in roles of knowledge Centre will likely change according to the needs of the user community and the level of technological sophistication.

Reference:

1. Wang Yunhua. Knowledge Economy and the Development of the library, Library Work & Research. 1999(6), 17-19
2. Cao Yi. The Reorientation of Libraries in the Knowledge Economy Era, Library Work & Research, 1999(3), 24-26
3. Wang Delu. The Collection and Processing of Knowledge. February 4,199. http://www.bsti.ac.cn/bsti_kmchina/gei /048_001.htm, accessed on dated March, 25, 2021
4. Sheng Xiaoping. Knowledge Management of Libraries in the 21st Century, Library Magazine, 1999 (8), 29-32

5. Corall, S 2000 'Are we in the knowledge management business' Ariadne Issue 18 *Knowledge Management* pg 1-8 (available in both web and print versions)
6. Horvath, J 2001 'Working with Tacit Knowledge' in the *Knowledge Management Yearbook 2001* pp 35-50.
7. Snowden, D 'A framework for creating a sustainable programme' in the IBM publication: *Knowledge management - a real business guide* Caspian :UK 1988
8. Sbarcea, Kim 2000 'Knowledge management in the trenches' Conference July 2000
9. Corall, S 2000 'Are we in the knowledge management business' Ariadne Issue 18 *Knowledge Management* pg 1-8 (available in both web and print versions)
10. <http://www.oneumbrella.com.au/>., accessed on dated March, 25, 2021
11. Bishop, Karen 'Leveraging our knowledge: the skills and attributes information service professionals bring to new roles in information and knowledge management'. ALIA 9th Specials, Health and Law Libraries Conference. Available online: <http://conferences.alia.org.au/shllc2001/papers/bishop.2.html>, accessed on dated March, 25, 2021
12. Bonner, Dede 'Enter the Chief Knowledge Officer.' *Training and Development*, Feb 2000, pp 36-40.
13. Broadbent, Marianne *The phenomenon of knowledge management: what does it mean to the information profession?* 1998. Available online:
14. <http://www.sla.org/pubs/serial/io/1998/may98/broadben.html>, accessed on dated March, 25, 2021
15. Butler, Yvonne 'Knowledge management - if only you knew what you knew'. *STRAIT to the future ALIA 8th Asia-Pacific Specials, Health and Law Librarians Conference*. Available online: <http://conferences.alia.org.au/shllc1999/papers/butler.html>, accessed on dated March, 25, 2021
16. Church, Doug. 'From librarian to knowledge manager and beyond: the shift to an end-user domain'. Available online:
17. <http://www.sla.org/chapter/ctor/courier/v36/v36n2a1b.htm>., accessed on dated March, 25, 2021
18. Houghton, Jan, Barbara Poston-Anderson, and Ross Todd 'From obsession to power: changing the face of librarians'. *Pathways to Knowledge, Australian Library and Information Association 5th Biennial Conference and Exhibition, 25-28 October 1998, Adelaide Convention Centre, Adelaide, South Australia*. 313-318.
19. Marconi, J 'Outside the square: library and information services innovations within a knowledge management context'. *ALIA 9th Specials, Health and Law Libraries Conference*. Available online:
20. <http://conferences.alia.org.au/shllc2001/papers/marconi.html>, accessed on dated March, 25, 2021
21. Milne, Patricia 'Information professionals and the knowledge-aware, intelligent organisation: skills for the future.' *Australian Library Journal* 49 (2), May 2000 139-150.
22. Skills for knowledge management a briefing paper by TFPL Ltd based on research undertaken on behalf of the [UK] Library and Information Commission. 1999. Available online: <http://www.lic.gov.uk/publications/executivesummaries/kmskills.pdf>., accessed on dated March, 25, 2021